

SOCIAL FACTORS DETERMINING CHANGES IN THE SPHERE OF MODERN ECONOMIC TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the systemic connections in this terminology and to present economic vocabulary in an organized form. In our opinion, scientific novelty lies in the attempt to comprehensively analyze this group of terminological vocabulary, in the volume and content that we have identified. The significance lies in the fact that the material is given in the volume and composition in which it functions in the modern Russian language and the results of the study can be used in conducting integrated lessons, which will allow diversifying the forms of training.

Keywords: economic terminology, vocabulary, lexical-semantic, term, systemic connections, linguistics, economic terms, organization.

Introduction

These days are the time of the loss of old economic dogmas, the time of the formation of a new economic model, the emergence of new professions in connection with this. The magic word "market", which sounded at the first congresses of people's deputies, symbolized this turn in economic development. It was followed by a whole avalanche of new "economic" words - chronological markers of the changes taking place. This avalanche swept away the boundaries of traditional narrow professional use and generously splashed out on book stalls in the form of numerous relevant publications on management and marketing, leasing and consulting, accounting and auditing. Economic terms sounded in oral speech on radio and television. Thus, most of the key economic terms turned out to be "on the lips" of a significant part of society. In these conditions, increased attention to the actively developing economic terminology system could not but arise, which, as it seems to us, determines the relevance of the chosen topic. The aim of the work is to explore systemic connections in this terminology and to present economic vocabulary in an organized form.

Methods

The modern stage of development of linguistics is characterized by an increased interest in the dynamic aspects of language and the transition to anthropocentric linguistics, which studies language in its relationship with man, his consciousness, thinking, and various types of activity. Significant changes are also taking place in the science of terms, as a result of which a new - cognitive - direction of terminology is being formed.

An appeal to the history of terminology shows that the emergence of this new direction was natural. Many general studies on the theory of terms present the main directions of terminology. It is generally accepted among researchers that terminology as an independent scientific discipline developed gradually as a result of the autonomous development of individual scientific directions with their subsequent synthesis. The leading directions - the constituent parts of terminology - were: methodological research, term theory, philological

studies of terminology, functional-stylistic studies of terminology, diachronic studies of terminology, ordering and standardization of terminology, terminography, scientific and technical translation, professional linguodidactics and industry studies of terminology.

Results and Discussion

The linguistic situation of the pre-stagnation 1960s differs radically in terms of research from the linguistic situation of our days. In recent decades, the process of replenishing the vocabulary of the Russian language has become unusually active. Among the new words, words of financial and economic terminology predominate: barter, broker, dealer, investments, marketing, monetarism, realtor, sponsor.

This vocabulary at each stage of development can be divided into two groups:

- codified units included in dictionaries;
- words used in texts (literary, journalistic, scientific, business).

Widely used in advertising, they go through the stage of written recording and are included in dictionaries.

An experiment in which 100 respondents were interviewed, giving an interpretation of economic lexemes, it was found that even the most frequently encountered words are not always familiar to native speakers or are only approximately familiar.

The meaning of the word "realtor" - "a company or agent engaged in real estate transactions" is familiar to 78 respondents. Apparently, we can conclude that the given words can already be considered as having entered the Russian literary language, since during the linguistic experiment it turned out that at least 60% of respondents can formulate their meaning.

Changes in the field of economics have led to a change in the interpretation of words in this area. Very often this is due to the disappearance of the definition of "capitalist" or the indications "under capitalism" "in capitalist countries". Thus, in the dictionary entry devoted to the word "bank", a part of the interpretation related to the commentary on the role of banks under capitalism and socialism is omitted; in the dictionary entry for the word "stock exchange", the part "in capitalist countries" is removed: the word "broker" is formulated more precisely.

The lexeme "marketing" is interpreted not as "a system of market research activities carried out by large capitalist companies", but as "an integrated approach to production management and product sales".

Similar changes have occurred with the definition of the meaning of the word "management" as "production management used in the USA and other capitalist countries", and a modern dictionary states that "management is a set of modern principles, methods and forms of production and sales management". In a similar way, the negative connotation in the interpretation of the lexemes rent, etc. is removed. We can even talk about the appearance of a positive connotation in the interpretation of several similar lexemes.

Currently, there are more than 1000 financial and economic concepts that have come into use in recent years and have been included in dictionaries.

Modern economic terminology, from the point of view of sources of formation, is divided into a number of groups.

A significant layer of lexical units can be identified that represent a certain constant fund of economic terminology (regardless of the type of economy). These words express basic general economic concepts and categories, for example: production, consumption, production relations, productive forces, capital, base, superstructure, demand, supply, goods, trade

turnover, cost, price, money, surplus product, budget, national income, export, import, etc. [11]

Some economic terms, neutral in their semantic structure, were used in Soviet times as attributes or realities of the capitalist economy: unemployment, inflation, indexation, cartel, concern, stock exchange, banker, etc.

An excessive increase in the mass of paper money in circulation compared to the real supply of goods; a general long-term increase in prices in capitalist countries, leading to a depreciation of money, caused by various reasons (an increase in state military spending, monopoly policy, etc.). Inflation reduces the standard of living of workers and exacerbates the economic and social contradictions of capitalist society.

Semantic transformations in vocabulary, along with the nomination of new realities, contribute to the expansion and enrichment of the vocabulary. The acquisition of a new meaning by a word can lead to the birth of a new word, thereby strengthening linguistic homonymy. Among the semantic processes, three main ones stand out: expansion of meaning, narrowing of meaning and rethinking. Indicative changes have occurred with many words long known to the language. For example, the word "market" has clearly expanded its meaning or compatibility. We are accustomed to associating the concept of "market" with the realities of Soviet life - collective farm, state farm. Today, the following have appeared: wholesale market, clothing market, municipal market.

Economic processes of recent years have caused many linguistic transformations. New forms of social relations have manifested themselves most actively in various semantic changes.

The word "stagnation" as a term denoting "a time of slow economic development" has also broken away from its original use (stagnation in the blood, congestion in the lungs) and has moved into the sphere of economic life.

Semantic processes in vocabulary also include the process of depoliticization of some groups of words. The semantics of words is being liberated from the political and ideological connotation of the word: business, merchant, entrepreneur, private trader have lost their negative ideological increments. They were usually previously supplied with a commentary relating these concepts to the life of a capitalist society.

A neutral word reflecting modern reality, entrepreneur in the early editions of the Dictionary of S.I. Ozhegov, N.Yu. Shvedova defined it as follows:

- a capitalist who owns an enterprise;
- an enterprising person, a businessman.

And a businessman in turn received a definition: a person who cleverly conducts his affairs, not being shy about the means to achieve his selfish goals. Here are excerpts from the latest version of the dictionary by S.I. Ozhegov, N.Yu. Shvedova entrepreneur:

- the owner of an enterprise, firm, and also generally an activist in the economic, financial environment;
- an enterprising and practical person.

But the meaning of the word businessman in the new formulation is a person who successfully (sometimes not being shy about the means) conducts business (stock exchange dealers, shady dealers). As we can see, the word "dealer", which retained a negative assessment, albeit somewhat softened, was replaced by a neutral one. Among the semantic processes in the vocabulary, the issue of changing meanings is especially important rethinking words.

Changes in the meaning of words occur in speech, which is based on the selection and combination of linguistic units. The selection is determined by the paradigmatic relations of these linguistic units, and their combination is determined by syntagmatic relations.

One of the most vital and socially significant processes occurring in the modern Russian language is the process of activation of the use of foreign words. It is necessary to talk about activation of the use of these words, and not only about new borrowings, since along with the emergence of neologisms, there is an expansion of the spheres of use of economic terminology.

According to L.P. Krysin, the conditions for borrowing are bilingualism, i.e., the result of territorial contact between two peoples. This also includes such types of speech activity as reading, translation, commenting on foreign press, participation in international conferences, congresses. Another condition for borrowing may be that a predisposition to accept new foreign vocabulary arises in society.

The collapse of the Soviet Union and communication with the Western world predetermined the borrowing of numerous financial and commercial terms: barter, voucher, dealer, distributor, investor, clearing, leasing, futures loans. This borrowing occurred due to the orientation towards the Western economic and banking system and the introduction of Russian financiers to international terminology. And due to the acute social relevance of the phenomena designated by these terms, the terms themselves go beyond the limits of professional usage and are widely used in the press, on radio and television.

Thus, the word "sponsor", which appeared in the mid-80s, joined a series of names with similar meanings by origin:

patron - impresario - entrepreneur - producer.

A sponsor was originally designated as a person or organization that provides financial support to the creative activities of artists, musicians, and painters; then the object of sponsorship began to be understood more broadly, but the component "provides financial support" was preserved.

The activity of keywords affects not only their word-formation potential, but also their connections with other words, actualizing certain relationships between words in the lexical system of the language.

Keywords should be considered words denoting phenomena and concepts that are in the focus of social influence. The keywords of our era include high-frequency proper names and common nouns. The latter are divided into 2 types:

- Words that receive high frequency and word-formation activity for a short period of time (month, week, etc.). For example: voucher, vouch erization, default.
- Words that are active, high-frequency for a long time (a year or more); they are more indicative in the economy during the transition to market relations, since they name phenomena that characterize them more deeply. For example: inflation, stagnation.

Methodological approaches that have developed in the development of individual paradigms become mutually complementary areas of description and analysis of the term, its role in the life of society and the individual.

Thus, the analysis of the main directions of terminology shows that, in general, the logic of the development of terminology "repeats" the main stages of the development of linguistics, which, in turn, confirms the legitimacy of our identification of a new stage in the development of terminology and its definition as cognitive terminology.

Conclusion

Thus, the modern era has actualized many processes in the language. Language and society, as a user of the language, are inextricably linked, but at the same time have their own laws of life support.

So the emergence of something new in the life of society, just like the knowledge of new objects and phenomena, causes the need for nomination, which entails the formation of new words and expressions in the language or the formation of new meanings in previously existing units of vocabulary.

The development of economic terminology depends on social conditions, in this case - the transition to market relations. But at the same time, the development of vocabulary is determined by intra-linguistic factors associated with the systemic nature of the language.

So the main methods of creating economic terms in the Russian language have remained the same as they were before: word formation, compounding, formation of compound names, borrowing. All these methods are actively used in naming new realities. In particular, the increasingly expanding international economic ties, which contribute to the increase in the fund of the lexical system, are becoming significant influencing the formation of lexical neologisms limitations for its use and optimal conditions for its existence and development.

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